

Web-based system for linking fresh graduate employability and industry demand

Dlkhwaz Othman Mohammed, Mohammed Shihab
School of Computing, Faculty of Engineering
Universiti Teknologi Malaysia
Sulimanyah, Kurdistan, Iraq

Doqu180053@uniq.edu.iq, Mohammed.shihab@uniq.edu.iq

Abstract— the Web-based system for linking fresh graduate employability and industry demand built for Students to assist the local Kurdish community's young enlightened and passionate souls, allowing them to reach their full potential and, in turn, contribute to the betterment and development of our community. The system will assist students in gaining skills and building a résumé by volunteering. The Web-based system for linking fresh graduate employability and industry demand will help students to gain more skills and self-confidence through volunteering, the system will provide many volunteering programs that help recently graduated or current students improve their skills in a place where they can develop. Volunteering allows students to receive hands-on experience in a new and exciting situation while also allowing them to specialize their talents in teamwork. According to Deloitte's research, 82 percent of hiring managers prefer volunteers, and 85 percent are willing to overlook other CV flaws if a candidate has volunteered. Students with volunteer experience not only boost their portfolios but also successfully stand out among other potential applicants when it comes time to fill these open positions. The System will assist students in learning to operate in a group, which is a crucial skill for the workplace. Students will benefit from the system in terms of improving their resumes and job prospects.

Keywords — Volunteering Opportunities System, Youth empowerment, Organization, Internship, Skills development, Skills, Youth empowerment, Résumé enhancement.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, volunteering has grown in popularity. The majority of the students took part in team activities and are expected to become tomorrow's leaders. Volunteering builds students' human capital, improving their job prospects (Miller, Rocconi, & Dumford, 2018) and adding to their resumes (Handy et al., 2010). My goal is to recognize the importance of volunteering and to prepare the students for their future. Therefore, a new system will be established, students can find volunteering programs in their desired fields and beliefs. The goal is to create a Student Volunteering Program System that will help students find work as volunteers and connect with the organization and programs. Ensure students benefit from the system and settle on a comprehensive plan for improving the system. Volunteering boosts students' leadership abilities, critical thinking skills, self-confidence, and conflict resolution abilities greatly during their undergraduate years (Kilgo, Sheets, & Pascarella, 2015).

II. BACKGROUND OF THE PROBLEM

The Kurdistan Region (KRG) has been through a lot since 1991, from war to economic collapse and crises, and the young generation has been affected. It has shaped the minds and perspectives of this generation, which is growing up with hopes and dreams of being able to allow their inner creativity, inner passion, and life-changing ideas to come to life with only a helping hand to assist them along the path. There is a saying that if you have finished university, you have a job. in reality, almost 53% of college graduates are unemployed. The average college graduate takes three to six months to find work after graduation. A student who has gained a career-

search strategy and has prior work experience has a significant advantage. Otherwise, her resume might be lost for a specific position if she doesn't do something. The main problem is that the current education guides Students do not all work their way through college This has caused students to lack of experience when they graduate. Many job vacancies require some depth of experience when they offer an entry-level position. Even if you have a bachelor's degree and a general understanding of your field, it isn't enough. According to a recent analysis of roughly 4 million job advertisements posted on LinkedIn since late 2017, 35% of "entry-level" openings required years of relevant employment experience. Besides that with experience, some jobs require valuable skills, some of which can only be gained when you work. Those with no work experience start the job market with a resume that they do not have enough skills. When it comes to taking positions, employers look for specific skills. They ignore a weak resume. Soft skills are what employers look for in graduated students, "Personal, interpersonal skills teamwork, listening, and communication – so-called "soft skills" (Khasanzyanova, 2017).

To give a planned and practical approach for both students and Organizations to connect, this project makes an effort to address the problem and other concerns associated with it. This project will focus on developing a website that will allow volunteering jobs to students all around Kurdistan the system will help students gain more skills and self-confidence through volunteering, and the system will provide many volunteering programs that help recently graduated or current students improve their skills in a place where they can develop.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review for this research is discussed in the chapter that follows [1-4]. It is a crucial chapter because it discusses in full all the necessary information needed to carry out this project. A literature review often involves a selective appraisal of recently published research that is pertinent to the proposed system. In other words, it demonstrates the procedure for locating, acquiring, and analyzing the data required for system development. Additionally, it provides rationale and explanations that aid in resolving issues in the field of study. Several subjects will be covered in this chapter. These comprise an overview of the organization's case study, an analysis of the current system, a comparison with the current system, and the technology, tools, and methodology utilized to create the new system. Besides, this very chapter enables us to specify the key units that play a crucial function in the progress of this system. To research and compare compatible systems to the NextPhase system which has

identical components and procedures. The research and comparison have been done to modify these procedures to figure out the issues that have been examined in chapter one with unique technologies and promising concepts to manufacture the project.

Three similar systems are currently being discussed. There are different features for these 3 similar systems and applications. This section deals with the background information acquired on different systems This information is utilized to compare and develop the Volunteering Opportunities System with Similar systems. The existing system is set up in such a way that users will have access to more features that are more user-friendly. This page covers some of the studies conducted by several researchers to understand the concept of manual, traditional, or volunteer job procurement. Finding volunteer work usually includes a combination of approaches, such as personal relationships, direct phone calls to businesses, and visits to a job agency office (Mansourvar and Mohd, 2010). The current system saves students time and money that they would have spent manually visiting companies to look for employment openings. As well as the time and money spent by organizations on making posters and paying radio stations for announcements.

A. *Reed.Co.Uk*

Reed.co.Uk is an application/Website where you can search for a job based on your location and field, user will get full information about the organization and the job before applying. User can register and manage their account by adding their detail including their resume. Moreover, the user will be able to add status according to their availability or unavailability

B. *CatchaFire*

Catchafire is a professional volunteer subscription service available online. COVID-19 basics, Finance and operations, fundraising, human resources, marketing and communications, professional development, program management, and technology are some of the areas where you can help are among the services provided. Catchafire is a platform that connects professionals who want to volunteer their time with NGOs that require their expertise.

C. *Job portal*

The system has two links: "Company" and "Candidate," which allow recruiters and job searchers to register as new users and login to the system, respectively. This page also has a "Search Job" button that permits job seekers to search for job openings without logging into the system. Users will be able to look for and view open positions that have been registered or saved in the system. Filters are also available on this page to assist users in finding what they're looking for more easily and

quickly. Organizations can use filters or skills to look for job seekers who have registered in the system. The page shown below will allow recruiters to look for applications.

Table III-1: COMPARISON OF EXISTING SYSTEMS AND PROPOSED SYSTEM

Features	Reed.co.uk	CatchaFaire	Job Portal	NextPhase
Deployment	Mobile Application/ Website	Website	Website	Website
Technology	Mobile Application Technology/ Web technology	Mobile Application Technology/ Web technology	Mobile Application Technology/ Web technology	Mobile Application Technology/ Web technology
Platform	Android & IOS	Windows & Mac	Windows & Mac	Windows & Mac
Connectivity	Online	Online	Online	Online
Security features	OTP Verification	OTP Verification	OTP Verification	OTP Verification, Authentication and Authorization, Password Hashing, and, Data Validation.
User Friendly	YES	YES	YES	YES

IV. METHODOLOGY

Methodology is a crucial factor that must be focused on to ensure a planned and efficient growth process. It's a software development method. It also serves as a roadmap to ensure that the system's development stays on track. The process of constructing a system will be easier to organize with a methodology, minimizing the system development cost, maximizing the development duration, and fulfilling the objectives through time management.

This chapter discusses the methodology used in the development of the Volunteering Opportunities System. It is critical to select a methodology that is appropriate for the project because it will determine how the project development

process will be carried out, beginning with the first phase and ending with the production of a working system. In its most basic form, software development methodology is a way of planning, organizing, and managing the development of a system. The methodology also refers to the specific outputs and artifacts that development teams produce and complete.

The most appropriate process model for developing the Volunteering Opportunities System is iterative development. This is because iterative development is based on the methodical repetition of small cycles known as iterations. Its goal is to build a favorable product that will meet the needs of the people. This project followed the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), which began with a simple implementation and gradually increased in complexity and feature set until the final system was completed. It demonstrates that an iterative model does not begin with a complete set of requirements. According to the Software Development Life Cycle, In the creation of software, there are five stages (SDLC). The steps include Requirement Analysis, Design, Implementation, Testing, and Evaluation.

A) Iterative development

The iterative development process does not follow a rigid process as it is cyclical. The initial planning is not required to be well-defined and proceed to the iteration of each phase of SDLC with extensive testing until the system behaves as the developer desires. This step of iteration allows the developers to review and change the previous cycle until it meets all the requirements. There are five steps in iterative development which start with Planning and Analysis, Design, Implementation, Testing, and Evaluation.

Figure IV-1: Iterative Development Phases

1) Planning and Analysis

The step of planning and analysis is where the project's planning is stated. The project's goals, scope, and context were all established at the beginning. During this phase, it is also necessary to compare the existing Volunteering Job Opportunities. Estimating the resources is also required, as well as a Gantt chart that displays all of the tasks. Important dates must be provided. Aside from that, a questionnaire survey of the community is being conducted. To collect the

requirements, the Volunteering Opportunities system will be used. users' viewpoints.

2) Design

The major goal of the design phase is to set technical requirements for the system's architecture. The requirements for the Volunteering Opportunities system will be defined when the online survey has been analyzed. Then there's the use case for the project can also be determined and UML diagrams produced. At the same time, the functional and non-functional needs are documented. SRS. After that, the design phase begins. During this phase, the system's initial design is completed. The design, architecture, database, and user interface are all determined. The Software Design Specification (SDS) is a document that describes the software that is (SDD).

3) Implementation

Methodology is a crucial factor that must be focused on to ensure a planned and efficient growth process. It's a software development method. It also serves as a roadmap to ensure that the system's development stays on track. Following the completion of the previous phases, the implementation phase will begin. During this phase, the code will be written utilizing the technologies and tools chosen during the system's development. HTML, CSS, JS, PHP, and Mysql were used in this project to create the Volunteering Opportunities system. To verify that there are no errors, the implementation and testing phases will be repeated side by side. If there are any errors in the code, it can be rewritten till it meets the requirements and then moved on to the next iteration after testing.

4) Testing

During the testing phase, potential problems and issues for the Web-based system for linking fresh graduate employability and industry demand may be discovered. Furthermore, user acceptance testing thoroughly tests all of the functionalities (UAT). A completed report will be generated at the end of this phase, indicating that the system has been tested

5) Evaluating

The purpose of the evaluation phase is to move the software product from the development community to the user community. When the Volunteering Opportunities System is released to the end user, a problem frequently arises, requiring the development team to create a new product and amend the problems to satisfy the user's needs. Before the system is properly released, it must be ensured that all user manuals, system reports, and relevant diagrams are in.

Figure V-1: Use Case Diagram for VOS

The structure and behaviors of a system's operation are described by its architecture, which is a conceptual design. Actors or users who interact with this system. The levels are represented by three layers: are data access layer, the application layer, and the business logic layer. Within the system, each layer has its own set of rules and unique characteristics and responsibilities. The application layer represents the system's User Interface. This layer allows the user to engage with the system and obtain access to its functions. The business logic layer serves as a controller between the application layer and the data access layer. This layer checks user input and transfers data from the application layer to the data access layer.

Figure V-2: 3 layered Architecture of the system

V. DESIGN AND INTERFACES

The NextPhase System will be further analyzed and designed in this chapter. A user case diagram, a sequence diagram, a class diagram, a UML diagram, and an interface diagram are among the diagrams that will be generated.

A use case diagram is used in the VO System to represent the relationship between an actor and their actions or functions. Each performer has a distinct personality and mannerisms. Each entity is separated by the module.

I. Interface Design

In the interaction between humans and computers, the importance of interface design cannot be overstated. The goal of the interface is to show how the system works. Furthermore, user-friendly design is required to ensure that users can access and interact with system functionalities quickly and effortlessly.

VI. TESTING AND DISCUSSION

The process of system development in terms of coding based on the system definition is the focus of the implementation and testing. This procedure should be followed after determining the system's objectives and requirements. should follow the rules. To fix the bugs, the development and testing were done iteratively. existing flaws or errors as quickly as possible.

To begin, all of the necessary development tools, such as Visual Studio Code and the Xampp package, were downloaded. As it is implemented in both mobile and web-based applications, this technology aids in the development of the Volunteering Opportunities System. The project structure featured an index HTML file that serves as the system's main entry point, a root module for system control, and pages made up of HTML, JS, and CSS files.

After that, the implementation phase began with the creation of a user interface for each function. The HTML and CSS files in each page's folder are primarily coded in this step. The interfaces aid in tracking the flow of the Volunteering Opportunities System's many functions. After the APIs were set up, a new MYSQL project was built to contain all of the relevant data. In order to communicate with MYSQL from the Front-End. After setting up MYSQL, the organization began implementing the system backend for each function, such as login, registration, search, apply for volunteer positions, manage account settings, view all system actions, and track students.

During the testing phases, the system's implementation was discussed. To identify any system defaults, Black Box testing and User Acceptance Testing were performed. The testing process is therefore essential in locating and removing any potential flaws in the developed system in order to ensure system quality.

A) Black Box Testing

Because the focus is on the input and output generated by the system, black box testing does not require a tester to understand what is happening on the code side. This determines how the system responds to expected and unexpected user behaviors, as well as reaction time, usability, and reliability concerns. This testing evaluates critical subsystems such as the user interface/user experience (UI/UX), web server or application server, database, and integrated system. Black box testing focuses on data key-in during user, application, audit module, and other updates, additions, and deletions.

Table VI-1:Blackbox for Registration

Input	Expected Results	Actual Results	Results
Click the "Register" button after	The message "Successfully registered" is	The message "Successfully registered"	Pass

Figure V-3: Home Page

Figure V-4: UI for Volunteer Panel as Edit Profile

Figure V-5: UI for Search for Internship

Figure V-6: Organization Panel

entering a valid username, password, and confirm password.	displayed, followed by a redirect to the login page.	appears on the screen, and the user is redirected to the login page.	
If the username, password, and confirm password are all the same, click the "Register" button.	The warning "Invalid username" is displayed.	The warning "Invalid username" is displayed.	Pass
Click the "Register" button after entering a valid username, password, and confirm password.	The notice "Failed to set password alert" appears.	The message "Failed to set password" appears.	Pass

B) White box testing

White box testing is a process where the internal configuration, coding, and structure of the software are examined to confirm an input and output flow and enhance design, usability, and security. One advantage of employing white box testing is code optimization through the identification of hidden errors. White box testing is used to check the efficiency of the Volunteering Opportunities System's system flow. To accomplish the goal in this case, a path coverage is used.

Table VI-2: White Box Testing for Registration

Node	Flows
1	Fill in user information
2	this.afAuth.auth.createUserWithEmailAndPassword(username, password)
3	this.showAlert("Success!", "You are successfully registered")
4	header("Location: register-candidates.php");
5	if (password !== Upassword)
6	this.showAlert("Error!", "Password don't match")
7	End

Figure VI-1: Nodes of UC001- Registration

C) User Acceptance Testing

User Acceptance Testing (UAT), often known as end user testing, is a method of determining if software is acceptable or not. A final test is run after the functional, system, and regression tests have been completed. The goal of the testing is to ensure that the system meets the organization's requirements. Validation testing is carried out by end users who are familiar with the business requirement.

Table VI-3: User Acceptance Test for Register Module

TC #	Input	Expected Result	Pass/Fail
	Leave all field empty, click "Register" button	Display Error Message "Invalid username"	Pass
	Enter name, phone number, password and confirm password. Click "register" button	Display Error Message "Invalid username"	Pass
	Enter username as "admin", name as "Dlkhwaz", phone number as "00000000", password and confirm password. Click "register"	Display Error Message "Invalid username"	Pass

button			
Enter username as “Dlkhwazothman@gmail.com”, name as “Dlkhwaz”, phone number as “111111”, password and confirm password. Click “register” button	Display “Successfully Registered” and redirect to login page	Pass	

VII. CONCLUSION

The project began with a survey of students from several universities. The goal is in order to obtain a better knowledge of the situation of the proposed system and benefits of volunteering towards students for their Future perspective. After the procedure is finished, the background of the problem, as well as the present status and system, are identified, leading to a proposed solution for resolving such problems.

The literature review is discussed in the following chapter. An analysis of the current system as well as three other systems that are currently being used, was conducted during this section. The systems chosen are similar to the proposed system in terms of features and processes. All elements and characteristics that might be useful are added in the proposed system during the analysis Searching for jobs using filters, applying online, and the technology employed are examples of aspects and features that have been combined with the proposed system. In addition, we reviewed the technology that is now in use on existing systems in this chapter. Xampp and VS code, among others, are part of the technology.

In Chapter 3, the system methodology is explained in full. The chosen approach, Iteration Development Methodology, has been explained and justified about the chosen model. Starting with the Planning and Analysis phase and ending with the Evaluation phase, all aspects of the chosen approach are addressed. In addition, an Analysis of Software Requirements, that incorporates hardware and software, was presented in this chapter.

The most crucial aspects of the system are covered in Chapter 4. The analysis and design of systems are covered in this chapter. that includes everything from system flow, database design, and diagrams to requirements analysis (use case, sequence, and activity), among other things. This chapter also includes an early interface design for the planned system.

The project's conclusion is detailed in Chapter 6. The Goals of the Project and Suggestions for Future Improvement are the topics of this chapter.

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